

QUIZ**LAST NAME: SENESI****FIRST NAME: ROSELYNN****PROGRAM CODE: MDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MS Word 365, Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Objective presentation of work helps to do what in your paper ?**

It eliminates personal interest in the subject matter¹

It reinforces connection between facts

It supports free flow of ideas.

It creates proper paragraphing.

2. **How will you reinforce scholastic style in research writing?**

By using personal examples of other authors.

By quoting ideas from other researchers.

By paraphrasing ideas and information from other researchers.

By using logical- objective connectors in your paper.²

¹ Laurent Cleenwerck and Karibu Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2019), 12.

² Ibid,13.

3. **In research, which of the following is the fundamental stage?**
- Draft Printing.
 - Draft planning.
 - Draft Revision.**³
 - Budget Planning.
4. **Which one of the following will significantly help define your argument in the research?**
- Availability of resources.
 - A standard Planning Path.**⁴
 - Accessibility to data.
 - Qualification of the researcher.
5. **The most important reason why it is relevant for researchers to understand the required task of the research is?**
- To be able to stay within the scope of the mandate.**⁵
 - To be able to collect evidence.
 - To be able to seek answers to your queries.
 - To be able to discover hidden scenarios related to your work.
6. **What advise would you likely give a student of research on a better way to avoid unintended plagiarism?**

³ Kate L. Turibian, *A Manual for Writers for Research Papers Thesis, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 68.

⁴ Ibid, 42.

⁵ Ibid, 36.

- To create an accurate and comprehensive reference list of all works cited in the paper.⁶**
- To create established path of the research methodology.
- To consult published work of other researchers.
- To include more citations in the paper.
7. **In a research work, what relevance do you think citations will have on your paper?**
- Citations will help improve readership of my paper.
- Citations will help to measure the contextual impact on my paper.⁷**
- Citations will help determine my writing ability.
- Citations will help eliminate any potential problems I may have to encounter in my work.
8. **Why are researchers guided against oversimplification and overemphasization of a case in a research work?**
- To reduce expenditure on stationary.
- To be able to finish work on time.
- To reduce critical mistakes in the paper.
- To avoid the risk of weakening the**
- interest of the readership in the paper.⁸**

⁶ Kate L.Turibian, 208.

⁷ Lauren Cleenewerck and Karibu Gulma, *ACA- 401 Coursework: Period 4* (Bangui Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 54.

⁸ Lauren Cleenewerck and Karibu Gulma, 9.

9. **What negative effect will an irrelevant information have on your paper?**

- It will lead to misrepresentation of the facts in my paper.
- It will confuse the readership of my paper.
- It would be inappropriate and could have the potential to downgrade my paper.⁹**
- It will cause delay in the submission of my paper.

10. **The primary objective for the periodic development of the English Style Guide by the European Commission in the EU is?**

- To guide workers in the European Union on how to overcome the cryptic and bureaucratic language of diplomacy.¹⁰**
- To enhance the adoption of more draft resolutions in the European Union.
- To foster more cooperation among workers at the European Union.
- To help the facilitation of the convening of more meetings in the European Union.

⁹ Cleenewerck Laurent and Karibu Gulma, 7.

¹⁰European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Union*. 7th edition (European Union, 2011), 1.

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